

THE EFFECT OF TEACHERS' WORK-LIFE BALANCE ON ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR

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Abstract:

The role of teachers in the education of the desired quality cannot be denied. The behaviors that teachers will exhibit within the organization are important. However, it is thought that life at work and outside of work also affects these behaviors. The research was conducted with a quantitative approach and organizational citizenship behaviors and work-life balance levels were determined from the teachers' point of view. In addition to this, analyzes were conducted to what extent work-life balances predicted organizational citizenship behaviors. The research was conducted in relational survey model. The sample of the study consists of 535 teachers working in public, kindergarten, primary, secondary and high schools in Ödemiş district of İzmir. In the study, "Organizational Citizenship Behavior Scale" and "Work-Life Balance Scale" were used. As a result of the research, the levels of organizational citizenship behavior of teachers are positive but not very high. Work-life balance levels are moderate. No correlation was found between teachers' general work-life balance and organizational citizenship behaviors. However, very low level correlation was found between some sub-dimensions of work-life balance and organizational citizenship behavior. It was revealed that work-life balance's "neglecting life" sub-dimension positively low level, "allocating self-time" and "life consisting of work" sub-dimensions negatively low level predicted organizational citizenship behavior. From this point of view, although there is no direct effect of work-life balance in general, it shows that other conceptual variables that affect sub-dimensions may have a greater impact on organizational citizenship behavior and the need to investigate the effects of these concepts.

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1. Introduction

Human factor plays an important role in increasing the success of communities and organizations. In today's world, where competition is draconian, as a factor of corporate success, voluntary behaviors are important, rather than defining roles in their jobs. These behaviors are basically defined as "Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)" (Karaman & Aylan, 2012). The altruistic behaviors of the employees have positive effects on the organizational success. Organizational Citizenship Behavior is based on altruistic behaviors and expresses the positive behaviors of the employee for the benefit of the organization without the expectations of personal interests and merit. It has been found that employees who exhibit OCB have positive contribution to organizational performance (Williams & Anderson, 1991). Employees' life outside the organization has also a major impact on this performance within the organization. It is known that business life also affects employees' life outside work. For this reason, the relationship between quality in working life and employee's life has always been the focus of attention. The degree of influence of these concepts to each other is also important because of their impact on both sociology of society and company performance. The concept of "Work-Life Balance (WLB)", which focuses on maintaining a balanced life for employees, is being investigated in the sphere of influence of different problems due to social, cultural and demographic changes. As women have started to work in the labor market, there is an increase in the number of families in which both parents work. Increasing importance given to psychological agreements and occupational safety measures between employees and organizations increased the importance of WLB. While the positive contributions of WLB provide an increase in employee performance in organizations, adversities in WLB lead to an increase in the number of psychologically disturbed and dissatisfied employees. The pressures in the workplace, the increasing demands of the workplace can lead to some conflict between employees' work and their personal roles. Correct implementation of WLB and policy-making organizations can be more successful at financial level. In addition, WLB has effects such as decreasing absenteeism rate of employees, increasing efficiency and customer satisfaction levels and increasing morale motivation of employees.

The main objective of WLB is to create harmony between work and family and to provide maximum opportunity for employees to demonstrate their professionalism at the maximum level (Sudha & Karthikeyan, 2014). Existing studies show that OCB is of great importance for organizational success today. Organizations expect their employees to perform altruistic behaviors in the form of organizational citizenship in addition to their normal duties. These expectations sometimes create conflicts with the concept of WLB. Nowadays, the gap in WLB literature can weaken its theoretical foundations in terms of linking it to organizational results such as OCB. There is also a need to examine how the OCB levels of education workers are affected by the WLB.

Although literature investigates teachers' perceptions of OCB and WLB on the basis of different variables, there are not many studies examining the relationship between these two variables and their effects on each other. In this study, it is aimed to determine the relationship between OCB and WLB, to determine whether the WLB's effect on OCB in the working environment, to contribute to the literature by bringing findings and recommendations based on findings.

1.1 Organizational Citizenship Behavior

The concept of organizational citizenship behavior was first defined in the literature by Organ (1988) as a collection of individual behaviors that voluntarily contribute to the effective functioning of organizations, apart from the formal reward system. Volunteering is always the essence of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). OCB is a voluntary employee behavior that helps the employees and the workplace in all aspects of the organization with open communication skills (Yen, Li & Niehoff, 2008). Although not planned in the organization's reward system, these voluntary behaviors contribute positively to the functioning of the organization (Bateman and Organ, 1983). OCB is defined as behaviors exhibited by employees beyond the roles of employees defined in the organization (Tood, 2003). In other words, it can be expressed that employees are constructive in actions other than their roles and avoid avoiding negative effects on organizations (Kaplan, 2011; Karacaoğlu & Güney, 2010).

In organizations where OCB is applied effectively, a good working atmosphere is achieved, the quality of the environment increases, and the number of employees quitting is reduced and employees integrated with the organization are gained. Acquisition of such an environment enables the successful employees in the field outside the organization to be brought into this environment and increases the success of the organization. The success of the organization is related to the qualifications of the employees rather than the quantity in the material values. Successful employees voluntarily contributing to the functioning of their organizations will increase the success of organizations (Sezgin, 2005). Similarly, in schools with a good working environment and student portfolio, teachers who have a good career want to work. In such an environment, OCB can be a factor that increases organizational success.

OCB has also negative effects on organizations. Excessive OCB of the employees may lead to disruptions in performing the official duties required by their jobs and consequently failures. The reward system applied to employees exhibiting OCB can create pressure on other employees by creating a competitive environment (Karaman ve Aylan, 2012). For this reason, it can be said that they exhibit OCB as a good example when they can show positive behaviors towards employees, organizations and other employees (Akdoğan & Köksal, 2014).

1.2 Organizational Citizenship Behavior of Teachers

The OCB seen in teachers may differ according to the OCB of other employees. In education, OCB is shaped around the subdimension of altruism. DiPaola & Costa Neves (2009) reported that teachers routinely exhibit altruistic behavior to both individuals

and students as part of their profession. For the realization of organizational goals, the students are the focus of the schools. Any altruistic behavior that will be exhibited against the student will ensure the development of the organization. Altruistic behaviors routinely performed by teachers are realized as a requirement of the teaching profession. These behaviors emerge as a natural consequence of such a presupposition. Schools benefit from teachers' OCB in creating academic and economic resources (Yılmaz, 2009). The repetition of OCB over time contributes positively to the effectiveness of organizations (DiPaola & Neves, 2009). Teachers' OCB increases the level of success by making schools more innovative, flexible and effective.

As a result, OCB is a behavior that has positive effects on both employees and organizations (Karaaslan et al., 2009). The positive behavior of the employees is based on the assumption that the OCB will make significant contributions to the achievement of the objectives of the organizations (Aslan, 2008).

1.3 Work-Life Balance

The concept of work-life balance (WLB) has been perceived as the absence of conflict between work and life in the historical process. According to Clark (2000), WLB is an equal participation of individuals in their job and family roles; as a result, they are equally satisfied. According to Kalliath & Brough (2008), WLB is the absence of interference between work and life, in other words, the absence of conflict. On the other hand, Voydanoff (2005) stated that WLB is that the work and family resources meet each other's demands and that participation in both dimensions is high.

Organizations invest in their lives according to the level of commitment they see in their employees (Jena & Pradhan, 2014). Organizations can show interest to the lives of employees by implementing IDA programs, so that employers' perceptions of employees can develop positively (Grover & Crooker, 1995). In WLB, the feeling and satisfaction of the employee in both the work and life dimension are related to the fact that both dimensions can cost each other. This level of work and life can be expressed as in balance.

WLB can also be defined by a variety of approaches. One of these approaches is the resources-demands approach. If the employee's job-based role cannot meet the demands from the family, this is defined as a work-family conflict, otherwise it is defined as family-work conflict (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985). Business-family conflict is two-way concepts. Each can affect the other (Voydanoff, 2004). However, it is the work-related problems that are more effective in work-family conflict, and family intervention is more frequent. For this reason, the characteristics and working conditions of the work are of primary importance in order to understand WLB.

Another approach used in defining WLB is the role tension theory. According to this theory, the basic idea is that there are separate life dimensions in which people perform different roles in the work and life process. Individuals have limited resources to use in performing roles (Goode, 1960). For example; the time and energy devoted to the job role may not be the same as to realize the role of the family. Individuals want to do everything, but time and energy may not be enough. This can also cause role

conflicts. According to Goode, it is normal to experience role tension challenges. On the other hand, devoting time to other roles improves the social environment of the individual and may generate relative increases in income and success. In this way, it is proposed that it can create social and economic resources for the individual (Sieber, 1974).

Another WLB approach is conflict theory. Conflict theory argues that an individual's use of time and energy in a family-like role leads to poor performance due to reduced energy and time in the job role (Parasuraman & Greenhaus, 2002). In conflict theory, the relationship between work and family is like an equation with zero sum. The energy to be spent for the family cannot be sacrificed for work, and vice versa is true too (Friedman, Christensen, & DeGroot, 1998). There will be a decrease in the workplace performance of an individual who spends a lot of time and energy on his family. Developed work-life policies aim to save time for the work and the family in various ways so that employees can gain energy and thus reduce conflict levels (Yuile et al., 2012). In response to the benefits provided by organizations for their employees, employees respond to their extra time and energy by focusing more intensely on their jobs (Tsui, Pearce, Porter & Tripoli, 1997). Research confirms that increased organizational support for employees increases the organizational commitment of individuals and motivates employees to perform further in their work.

Reducing work stress on employees requires a combination of work and life-related issues. For this reason, both the work-life balance and work-life conflict concepts should be considered and evaluated together. WLB consists of different definitions between both work and home demands. In this context, Greenblatt (2002) described WLB as an unacceptable conflict between the demands of work and non-work roles. Work and life are in constant competition for the individual, but they have to walk together in a balanced way. Individuals have different roles in work and non-work life. Over time, these roles can put pressure on one another. This situation causes conflicts (Duxbury, 2003). Negative effects of workplace and non-work life on each other can negatively affect human relations and satisfaction levels of individuals. The most important factor in this is the increase in the time spent on one side, and the negative effects caused by the decrease in the time spent on the other side.

Success or failure in one of the WLB components can have positive or negative effects on the other component (Rotondo & Kincaid, 2008). Research shows that participation in both business and family activities has positive effects on the other component. Nowadays, as a result of research in WLB literature, positive effects have been formed on the physical and mental health, work life satisfaction and productivity of the employees (Thomas & Ganster, 1995). In addition to physical and mental health, the increase in the general welfare of the employees was found to be an important effect (Kossek et al., 2012).

It has been found that work-life imbalance causes changes in the behavior and attitudes of employees and leads to negative results in this (Akin, Ulukök & Arar, 2017). In order to find solutions to the negative consequences of work life imbalance, organizations implement employee-friendly WLB programs, thus trying to find

solutions to gain employees and ensure their work and family balance (Gündoğmuş, 2017). As a result, WLB-enabled employees find reductions in their willingness to leave (Gerçek et al., 2015).

1.4 Work-Life Balance of Teachers

WLB in teachers is one of the biggest challenges of today's world. Improvements in the quality of learning require teachers to constantly improve themselves. Teaching requires lifelong learning. The work of teachers is not limited to the time they spend in schools. He has to study at home to be prepared for the lesson he will teach one day later. In addition, students have to devote time to these tasks in their homes as they keep records about their development and carry out the tasks assigned to the commissions in the school. Teaching does not end with performing teaching tasks. In addition to professionally educating the students well, they provide the students with skills related to life and ensure that they are raised as good citizens. Teachers' self-sacrificing activities in educational activities are one of the important indicators that increase school success (Smyth, 1995).

Today, due to problems such as teaching, academic workload and career, it is seen as an extremely stressful profession and scientific researches are conducted on WLB of teachers. All these stresses in life cause work-life imbalance on teachers. In the work-life imbalance, a factor in the selection of teachers as a field of study is that women have a majority in this profession. The differentiation of different problems such as working conditions, status struggles and career compared to other occupational groups has made this field a profession group in which work-family conflict is investigated (Bragger et al., 2005). The limited opportunities for teachers to develop themselves professionally and to improve their career adversely affect their WLBs (Çokluk, 2003). On the other hand, high organizational commitment of teachers, healthy and strong relationships with other factors in WLB dimensions are important factors that ensure teachers' WLBs and achievements are high (Erdem, 2008). Teachers are also required to pay maximum attention to their health in order to provide the WLB. A stressed, ill and unhappy teacher cannot do his job well (Vähäsantanen, Saarinen & Eteläpelto, 2009).

The happiness of teachers is affected by many positive or negative problems such as school administration, inter-employee harmony, school ethics, and the degree of opportunities for professional development (Day et al., 2006). The vast majority of teachers love their work despite all these difficulties, but life is not just about working. WLB is for teachers not only to work overtime, but to live a balanced life without forgetting that they have a family and a life outside the school (Lee & Shin, 2017).

1.5 The Relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Work-Life Balance

Although there is no domestic or foreign scientific research directly related to the relationship between organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and work-life balance (WLB), there are some studies working on these variables in other professional groups

other than teaching. With this research, this gap in the literature was tried to be completed.

OCB is an important concept which is the subject of research among organizational behaviors. OCB defines employees' self-sacrificing behaviors according to their wishes beyond their officially defined roles in their work. This may contradict the concept of equilibrium that WLB provides to work across environments. According to (Pradhan, Jena & Kumari, 2016), the lack of space in WLB literature prevents this concept from forming a strong theory in terms of linking to organizational outcomes such as OCB. However, according to (Grover & Crooker, 1995), organizations can improve employees' perceptions of the organization and employer positively through their programs on WLB. Hence, WLB supports employees' organizational behaviors such as OCB. According to (Oladele, Abu-Abdissamad, Akeem & Alagbe, 2016), organizations are encouraging employees to implement OCB through WLB policies and practices.

If employees are exposed to work-life imbalances, they can expect personal attention and assistance from the organization in resolving this event. In addition, work life imbalance was found to be negatively associated with OCB (Turner, Lingard & Francis, 2009). Nevertheless, an employee with a balance in working life can create self-reinforcing motivation in the future of the organization by not increasing the personal discomfort that is part of the OCB (Wang & Walumbwa, 2007). According to (Carlson et al., 2013), there may be an increase in the desire to exhibit OCB among employees who have achieved work-family balance.

Today, the concept of organizational citizenship behavior towards teachers has been investigated with the interaction of different variables (Çelik, 2007; Titrek, Bayrakçı & Zafer, 2009; Yılmaz, 2009; Aslan, 2008; Oğuz, 2011; Avcı, 2015; Oğuz, 2011; Dussault, 2006; Somech & Ron, 2007; Zeinabadi, 2010; Wagner & Dipaola, 2011; Yeager, 2016; Gaddis, 2016). Similarly, there are studies examining the work-life balance of teachers and various occupational workers on the basis of various variables (Miryala & Chiluka, 2012; Priya, 2017; Amjad, Kundi, Qureshi & Akhtar, 2014; Pradhan, Jena & Kumari, 2016; Erdamar & Demirel, 2014; Yılmaz & Altinkurt, 2015; Kuzulu, Kurtuldu & Özkan, 2013; Gökkaya, 2014; Korkmaz & Erdoğan, 2014). However, the relationship between these two concepts and the necessity of empirical studies on the predictive levels of each other are clearly seen.

1.6 Purpose of the Research

The aim of this study is to determine the effect of teachers' work-life balance on organizational citizenship behaviors according to teachers' opinions. For this purpose, the following questions were sought:

- 1) What are the opinions of teachers about organizational citizenship behavior?
- 2) What are the opinions of teachers about work-life balance?
- 3) Is there a relationship between the opinions of teachers on work-life balance and sub-dimensions and their opinions on organizational citizenship behaviors?

- 4) To what extent do the opinions of teachers on work-life balance and sub-dimensions predict all of their opinions on organizational citizenship behaviors?

2. Method

In this section, information about the research model, population and sample selection, data collection tool and data analysis are given.

2.1 Research Model

This study is a descriptive relational survey model because it is a study to explain the effect of teachers' views on work-life balances on their views on organizational citizenship behavior. The most common research in the field of education is descriptive method screening (Gurbetoğlu, 2014). Descriptive-relational screening is a research model that shows the situation or event that occurs in researches as it is, the relationship between the variables that make up this situation, the effect of each other and the degree of this relationship (Kaya, Balay & Göçen, 2012).

2.2 Target Population and Sampling

The universe of this research consists of 1200 teachers who work in 103 public schools belonging to the Ministry of National Education in Ödemiş district of İzmir with a population of 150,000 in 2018-2019 academic year. The sample of the study consists of 535 teachers working in kindergarten, primary, secondary and high schools in the same district. Stratified sampling method was used to identify the participants in the sample. As the number of high schools is limited, all of them are included in the sample, while primary and secondary schools are grouped according to their being in district centers and villages. In the identified groups, the percentage of participants in the universe was determined. Theoretical sample size chart was used in the calculation of the sample. According to the table 95% confidence level in the universe of 1200 people, $\alpha = .05$ significance and 52% tolerance level of the required sample size was determined to be 466 people (Balci, 2018). Of the 1200 teachers in the universe, 840 teachers (70%) were reached, of which 63,69% were voluntarily involved, thus the sample size was determined as 535 for 95% confidence level, $\alpha = .05$ significance level and 5% tolerance level.

2.3 Instruments for Data Collection

In this study, 12-item 5-point Likert-type one dimension "Organizational Citizenship Behavior Scale (OCBS)" which was developed by DiPaola, Tarter & Hoy (2005) and adapted to Turkish by Taşdan & Yılmaz (2008) was used to determine the organizational citizenship behaviors of teachers. In addition, in order to determine the level of work-life balance (Apaydın, 2011), a 20-item 5-point Likert-type and four sub-dimension "Work Life Balance Scale (WLBS)" was used. On the organizational citizenship scale, the participants were given the right to respond "strongly disagree (1)", "disagree (2)", "moderate agree (3)", "agree (4)", "strongly agree". On the other

hand, the scale of work-life balance gave options to the participants as “I disagree (1)”, “I agree very little (2)”, “I agree slightly (3)”, “I strongly agree (4)”, “I fully agree (5)”. Both scales are five-point Likert-type scales. In these scales, the number of intervals ($5-1 = 4$) was found and the corresponding interval coefficient was calculated as $4/5 = 0.80$. In both scales, the 1st choice value is “1,00-1,79”, the 2nd option value is “1,80-2,59”, the 3rd option value is “2,60-3,39”, the 4th option value is “3,40-4,19” and the 5th option value is “4,20-5,00”. Means were interpreted with reference to these range values. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient for the reliability of OCBS was calculated as 0.908; The KMO value calculated to show that factor analysis is interpretable was found to be 0.98 and the result of Barlett Sphericity Test was 3186,314. However, as a result of the factor analysis confirming OCBS, the variance explained by one dimension is 58.23%. If there is a single factor in the scales, 30% or more of the explained variance may be considered sufficient (Büyüköztürk, 2011). However, according to the factor analysis of WLBS, the scale is four-dimensional and the total variance explained by these four dimensions is 61.75%. Cronbach's alpha coefficient, KMO and Barlett values indicate that the SRS was highly valid and reliable. In addition, Cronbach Alpha coefficient for the reliability of WLBS was calculated as 0.728. If the coefficient is found to be 0.7 or higher, the reliability of the scale is considered to be good (Kılıç, 2016). According to factor analysis, the scale has four dimensions and the total variance explained by these four dimensions is 61.75%. The KMO value calculated as 0.884 to show that factor analysis to be interpretable, and the Barlett Sphericity Test result was 2995,831. Cronbach Alpha coefficient, KMO and Barlett values indicate that WLBS is highly valid and reliable.

2.4 Data Analysis

SPSS 18.0 program was used to analyze the relationship and impact between teachers' organizational citizenship behaviors and work life balance. The level of significance in analyzes was tested at .05 and the findings were presented in tabular form for the purposes of the study. Descriptive statistics such as arithmetic mean and standard deviation of teachers' responses were calculated in order to reveal their opinions on organizational citizenship behaviors and work-life balance. Correlation (r) analysis was conducted to look at the relationship between organizational citizenship behavior and work life balance and sub-dimensions. Work life balance and its sub-dimensions were taken as the predictive variable and the variable of organizational citizenship behavior was taken as the predicted variable. Regression analysis was performed to see how much work life balance and its sub-dimensions predicted organizational citizenship behavior.

3. Findings

In this section, findings related to the sub-problems of the research are given. First of all, the response to the question “What are the opinion of teachers on organizational citizenship behaviors?”, are included in the findings of the mean and standard

deviation values of the answers given for 12 items of the Organizational Citizenship Behavior Scale (OCBS). These findings are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Findings Regarding Item Means of Organizational Citizenship Behavior Scale

Organizational Citizenship Behavior Scale Items		$\bar{x}$	SD
Md1	Teachers help students in their personal time	4,0355	,90600
Md2	Teachers do not waste most of the time	4,3981	,80982
Md3	Teachers help new teachers	4,3421	,78421
Md4	Teachers are willing to work in new boards established at school	3,5308	,96691
Md5	Teachers are willing to support extracurricular activities	3,0206	1,22151
Md6	Teachers come to work and meetings on time	4,2262	,84094
Md7	Teachers help replace teachers	4,0897	,92377
Md8	Teachers enter the class on time and use the lesson time effectively	4,2393	,81807
Md9	Teachers share information on various topics with their colleagues	4,2112	,86887
Md10	Teachers devote a lot of time to their own work	3,5738	,89614
Md11	Teachers work efficiently on the work boards of the school	3,9364	,89300
Md12	Teachers make constructive suggestions to improve the school	4,0991	,84772
General Average		3,9752	,61003

When Table 1 is examined, it is seen that the general arithmetic mean is ($\bar{x} = 3,97$; $SD=,61$), which corresponds to the perception of “agree” on the intermittent value scale.

As the second sub-problem, the response to the question “What are the opinions of teachers about work-life balance?”, there are findings regarding the mean and standard deviation values of the responses of the teachers who participated in the research for 20 items of the Work Life Balance Scale (WLBS). These findings are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Findings Regarding Item Means of Work Life Balance Scale

Sub Dimensions	Work Life Balance Scale Items	$\bar{x}$	SD
Work-Life Harmony	M1 I decide what my priorities are in my business life and I act accordingly.	4,3271	,7054
	M2 I can balance my work and my personal life.	4,2093	,8352
	M3 I believe that I manage business well	4,1383	,8093
	M4 I think I have appropriately allocated my time to both my work and private life	3,8953	,9160
	M5 I can do anything by planning my life well	3,8018	,9108
	M6 I do activities that I like in my work and private life	3,6224	1,0109
Average		2,7162	,6714
Neglecting Life	M7 I can't even find time for simple things during the day	2,7644	1,1270
	M8 I think I watch life from behind	2,4859	1,2584
	M9 I can't keep up with the intensity of my work	2,6074	1,1396
	M10 Since I try to do a lot of work at the same time, I sacrifice basic vital activities such as sleep, regular nutrition and movement.	2,8691	1,2726
	M11 Although I think that my life reflects the ideal way of life, I live with the thought that I missed something	3,0261	1,1800
	M12 I see myself as someone who only knows how to work and who doesn't live the rest of life	2,3140	1,2976
Average		3,6882	,4899

Allocating Self-Time	M13	"I would have been happier if I had done things that would make me happy," I think	2,2168	1,3315
	M14	In an ordinary day, I make unhealthy decisions about which jobs I will spend my time and energy on.	1,9775	1,1282
	M15	I have difficulty in my work because I do not compromise my private life.	1,5831	0,9139
	M16	Tensions arising from my work negatively affect my private life.	2,3065	1,2237
Average			2,5822	,6778
Life Consisting of Work	M17	I keep working on the weekends.	2,3308	1,2634
	M18	I leave work mostly late.	2,1831	1,2764
	M19	I miss out-of-work activities because of the time I spend on my work.	2,4859	1,2479
	M20	I spend weekends doing something with my wife and / or my friend	3,6149	1,1021
	Average			2,5014
General Average			2,9380	0,4477

When Table 2 is examined, it is seen that the general arithmetic mean is ($\bar{x} = 2,93$; $SD=,44$), which corresponds to the perception of "I agree very little" on the intermittent value scale. The scale has four sub-dimensions.

The first dimension of the scale, "Work-Life Harmony" subscale, corresponds to the "I agree very little" perception with its arithmetic mean ($\bar{x} = 2,71$; $SD=,67$). The second dimension of the scale, "Neglecting Life" sub-dimension, corresponds to the perception of "I strongly agree" with its arithmetic mean ($\bar{x} = 3,68$; $SD=,48$).

The third dimension of the scale corresponds to the perception of "I agree very little" with the arithmetic mean ($\bar{x} = 2,58$; $SD=,67$) of the sub-dimension of "Allocating Self Time". The fourth and last dimension of the scale corresponds to the perception of "I agree very little" with the arithmetic mean ($\bar{x} = 2,50$; $SD=,62$) sub-dimension of "Life Consisting of Work".

Pearson correlation analysis was used for the findings of the third sub-problem of the study "Is there a relationship between the opinions of teachers on work-life balance and sub-dimensions and their opinions on organizational citizenship behaviors". Correlation is a method that explains the relationship between two variables and its size, direction and importance. The Pearson coefficient is indicated by the symbol "r". The number "r" ranges from "-1" to "+1". Values approaching 1 indicate increased relationship strength (Erdoğan, 1998). The value approaching +1 indicates the perfection of the positive relationship; approaching -1 indicates the excellence of the negative relationship. If the value is 0.00, it means that there is no relationship between these variables. Relationship level between 0.00-0.30 is low level of relationship; between 0.30 and 0.70, the relationship is moderate; 0.70-1.00 means that the relationship is high (Büyüköztürk, 2011). In the correlation analysis, work life balance and the sub-dimensions of work life harmony, neglecting life, allocating self-time, life consisting of work and organizational citizenship behavior are examined and the results are given in Table 3.

Table 3: The Relationship between the Opinions of Teachers on Work-Life Balance and Sub-Dimensions and Their Opinions on Organizational Citizenship Behaviors

	OCB	WLBG	WLH	NL	AST	LCOW
OCB	1					
WLBG	-,035	1				
WLH	-,041	,839**	1			
NL	,188**	,534**	,237**	1		
AST	-,133**	,779**	,543**	,173**	1	
LCOW	-,138**	,763**	,532**	,169**	,631**	1

** . Marked correlations were significant (.01) (n = 535).

(OCB: Organizational Citizenship Behavior, WLBG: Work-Life Balance General, WLH: Work Life Harmony, NL: Neglecting Life, AST: Allocating Self Time, LCOW: Life Consisting of Work)

As seen in Table 3, there is no statistically significant relationship between teachers' work-life balance general and organizational citizenship behaviors according to the opinions of teachers participating in the research ($p > .01$). However, when the relationship between teachers' work life balance and sub-dimensions and organizational citizenship behavior are examined,

- **In terms of Neglecting Life (NL):** There is a significant, positive and low level relationship between the NL sub-dimension and organizational citizenship behavior ($r: 0.188, p < .01$). According to this, as teachers' neglecting life increases, OCB level increases.
- **In terms of Allocating Self Time (AST):** There is a significant, negative and low level relationship between AST sub-dimension and OCB ($r: -0.133, p < .01$). According to this, the level of OCB decreases as teachers allocate time devotes for themselves.
- **In terms of Life Consisting of Work (LCOW):** There is a significant, negative and low-level relationship between the sub-dimension of LCOW and OCB ($r: -0.138, p < .01$). According to this, as teachers' level of LCOW increases, the level of OCB decreases.

At this stage of the research, the findings and comments are given about the fourth sub-problem, "To what extent do teachers' opinions on work-life balance and sub-dimensions predict all of their opinions on organizational citizenship behaviors?" question and by this way, to the main problem of our research "The Effect of Teachers' Work-Life Balance on Organizational Citizenship Behavior". In this analysis, simple regression analysis was performed because of the predictive effect. If a single argument is used, these regressions are called univariate regression. The degree of force of the regression is expressed in R^2 and indicated by % (Büyüköztürk, 2011).

In the correlation analysis between OCB and WLB and sub-dimensions in Table 3, regression analysis was not performed for these variables since there was no relationship between OCB - WLBG and OCB - WLH sub-dimension. However, the relationship between NLB, AST and LCOW sub-dimensions of the WLB and OCB was determined and the degree to which these sub-dimensions predicted OCB was examined and the results are given in the table below.

Table 4: Simple Linear Regression Analysis Results of Work-Life Balance Neglecting Life Subdimension Predicting Organizational Citizenship Behavior (N = 535)

Predicted Variable	Model	B	Sd	Beta(β)	t	p
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	Constant	3,111	,197		15,784	,000
	Neglecting Life	,234	,053	,188	4,426	,000
R:0,188 R ² :0,035 F ₍₁₋₅₃₃₎ :19,590 p: .000						

Dependent Variable: Organizational Citizenship Behavior
 Independent Variable (Predictive): Neglecting Life (NL)

As it is seen in Table 4, the sub-dimension NL which is the independent variable, is a positive and significant predictor of OCB [R: 0,188; R²: .035; F (1-533): 19.590; p .000]. The sub-dimension NL of teachers' WLB explained 3.5% of the variance of the OCB (R²: 0.035). In other words, 3.5% of OCB is affected by NL sub-dimension of WLB. One unit change in teachers' sub-dimension of "neglecting life (NL)" of WLB leads to a positive change of 0.188 units on OCB (β :0,188).

Table 5: The Results of Simple Linear Regression Analysis of Work-Life Balance Allocating Self-Time Sub-Dimension Predicting Organizational Citizenship Behavior (N = 535)

Predicted Variable	Model	B	Sd	Beta(β)	t	p
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	Constant	4,284	,103		41,538	,000
	Allocating Self Time	-,120	,039	-,133	-3,096	,002
R:0,133 R ² :0,018 F ₍₁₋₅₃₃₎ :9,584 p: .002						

Dependent Variable: Organizational Citizenship Behavior
 Independent Variable (Predictive): Allocating Self Time (AST)

As it is seen in Table 5, the sub-dimension AST which is the independent variable, is a negative and significant predictor of OCB [R: 0,133; R²: .018; F (1-533): 9.584; p: .002]. The sub-dimension AST of teachers' WLB explained 1,8% of the variance of the OCB (R²: 0,018). In other words, 1,85% of OCB is affected by AST sub-dimension of WLB. One unit change in teachers' sub-dimension of "allocating self time (AST)" of WLB leads to a negative change of 0,133 units on OCB (β :-0,133).

Table 6: The Results of Simple Linear Regression Analysis of Work-Life Balance Life Consisting of Work Sub-Dimension Predicting Organizational Citizenship Behavior (N = 535)

Predicted Variable	Model	B	Sd	Beta(β)	t	p
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	Constant	4,315	,109		39,684	,000
	Life Consisting of Work	-,136	,042	-,138	-3,219	,001
R:0,138 R ² :0,019 F ₍₁₋₅₃₃₎ :10,319 p: .001						

Dependent Variable: Organizational Citizenship Behavior
 Independent Variable (Predictive): Life Consisting of Work (LCOW)

As it is seen in Table 6, the sub-dimension LCOW which is the independent variable, is a negative and significant predictor of OCB [R:0,138; R²:0,019; F(1-533):10,359; p: .001].

The sub-dimension LCOW of teachers' WLB explained 1,9% of the variance of the OCB (R²: 0,019). In other words, 1,9% of OCB is affected by LCOW sub-dimension of WLB. One unit change in teachers' sub-dimension of "life consisting of work (LCOW)" of WLB leads to a negative change of 0,138 units on OCB (β :-0,138).

4. Results, Discussion and Suggestions

In this study, teachers' opinions about organizational citizenship behaviors and work life balances were examined and the relationship between these opinions was examined and the effect of teachers' work life balance on organizational citizenship behaviors was tried to be determined.

The teachers who participated in the research have positive opinions about organizational citizenship behaviors. However, although the opinions of the participants are positive, it can be said that the level is not very high. On the organizational basis, teachers are highly qualified as time assessments, as well as performing educational activities and assisting other employees. In researches of Avcı (2015), Herren (2014), Sezgin ve Kılınc (2012), Oğuz (2011), Yılmaz (2010), Titrek et al. (2009), Çelik (2007), Dussault (2006), the organizational citizenship level of teachers are good (I agree) and it is consistent with our research results. The importance of organizational citizenship behavior in the success of organizations cannot be denied. Organizational citizenship behavior, which is always expected from teachers, is always more advanced. For this purpose, teachers should be motivated by the school administration as required, flexibility should be provided in the syllabus and working hours, activities outside the school should be supported and organizational citizenship behavior exemplary practices should be rewarded (DiPaola & Hoy, 2005). Organizational citizenship behaviors should be investigated in institutions where deficiencies and inadequacies have been determined and necessary motivation increasing measures should be taken to exhibit these behaviors.

The levels of work life balance of teachers are slightly below the middle level with "I agree very little" according to our research. Participant opinions are positive but not very high in level. (Polat & Özdemir, 2017; Maeran, Pitarelli & Cangiano, 2013; Watson & Hillison, 1991) 's works are also consistent with the results of the research. Opinions about work life balance were evaluated in four sub-dimensions. According to the participant responses given to the sub-dimension of work life harmony, it was determined that the priorities of the teachers between work and private life were determined and carried out in a balanced way. It can also be concluded that, by adjusting the workload well, by planning time in both work and private life, a worker can perform activities it enjoys in work and private life.

Participation in the neglecting life sub-dimension is high. The work intensity of the participating teachers is moderate. Therefore, teachers have problems in finding time. In addition, it was found that teachers sacrificed from sleep, nutrition and other vital activities and as a result they missed some things in life. However, despite all these

negativities, it can be said that teachers are generally individuals who enjoy life and know how to live.

Participation in the allocating self-time sub-dimension was low. According to the perception of the participants, teachers reflect the stress in the workplace to their lives. Similarly, a number of problems in private life cause mild problems in the workplace. Teachers experience low level of problems due to the intensity of work pace. However, it can be said that they can spare time for themselves and be happy. Participation in the sub-dimension of life consisting of work was low. According to the perceptions of the participant teachers, it can be said that due to the fact that some teachers leave the workplace late, they cannot allocate enough time for other vital activities, but these people still can spend the weekends with their families.

In the study, the correlation between organizational citizenship behavior and work-life balance and its sub-dimensions was examined by correlation analysis. There was no statistically significant relationship between organizational citizenship behavior of teachers and work-life balance in general. On the other hand, statistically significant low-level relationships were found between organizational citizenship behavior and some sub-dimensions of work-life balance. The sub-dimensions of the work-life balance, which are found to be related, are neglecting life, allocating self-time and life consisting of work. In their study, Oladele et al. (2016) found a high positive relationship between work-life balance and organizational citizenship behaviors. Depolo & Bruni (2015) found a similar and positive relationship in the study, while Wijewantha & Sangarandeniya (2014) found a moderate relationship in the study. It overlaps with the results of the study.

The effects of teachers' work life balance sub-dimensions on organizational citizenship behavior were examined by regression analysis. Here, the sub-dimensions of work life balance were examined as predictive variable and organizational citizenship behavior as predicted variable. It can be said that the sub-dimension of neglecting life, which is independent variable, explains 3.5% of the variable of organizational citizenship behavior which is dependent variable, in other words, it can be said that 3.5% of organizational citizenship behavior depends on the dimension of neglecting life. This effect can be stated that one unit change in the neglecting life sub-dimension creates a change of 0.188 units on organizational citizenship behavior. The neglecting life sub-dimension was found to be a positive and significant predictor of organizational citizenship behavior. It can be said that as the level of neglecting one's life increases, he shows his time and energy, which he does not use, by increasing the level of organizational citizenship behavior, albeit at a low level.

As the independent variable of work life balance allocating self-time sub-dimension, it can be said that organizational citizenship behavior explained 1.8% of the dependent variable, in other words, 1.8% of organizational citizenship behavior took place depending on the allocating self time dimension. This effect can be stated that one unit change in the dimension of allocating self time creates a change of -0.133 units on organizational citizenship behavior. The sub-dimension of allocating self time was found to be a negative and significant predictor of organizational citizenship behavior.

As the level of allocating self time increases, the time and energy spent by the employee for himself outside the work increases and the time and energy spent for the workplace and his colleagues decreases. It can be said that this situation causes a decrease in the level of organizational citizenship behavior. Pradhan, Jena & Kumari (2016) found that work-life balance positively affects organizational citizenship behaviors and there is a significant relationship between them. However, they found that social and personal needs and personal interests were negative predictors in various sub-dimensions of organizational citizenship behavior. Similarly, Bragger et al. (2005) found that teachers examined organizational citizenship behaviors and work life conflict. He also found that the increase in employees' sense of role conflict had a negative effect on organizational citizenship behavior. It partially overlaps with the results of the study.

Work life balance is the independent variable of life consisting of work sub-dimension, it explains 1.9% of the dependent variable of organizational citizenship behavior, in other words 1.9% of organizational citizenship behavior occurs depending on the dimension of life consisting of work. This effect can be expressed as one unit change in the dimension of life being work creates a change of -0,138 units on organizational citizenship behavior. It has been found that the dimension of life consisting of work is a negative and significant predictor of organizational citizenship behavior. The sub-dimension of life being work has a negative effect on perceptions of organizational citizenship behavior. The fact that the dimension of life consisting of work is conceptually and functionally associated with the concept of workaholism, and even includes the effects of the concept of professional burnout; it shows us the negative effects on organizational citizenship behavior. According to Pekdemir & Koçoğlu (2014), there is a low level relationship between workaholism and work-life balance. They stated that there was a deterioration in work-life and life-work levels when there was an increase in the level of workaholism, which led to a work-life conflict. It can be said that burnout and depersonalization, which can be a factor in the occurrence of work-life conflict, indirectly have a negative effect that will cause a decrease in organizational citizenship behaviors. In this context, Chiu & Tsai (2006) 's research showed that employees who experience emotional exhaustion and depersonalization decrease their desire to realize organizational citizenship behaviors and cause a decrease in their personal success. This result is consistent with the results of our research on the negative effect of life consisting of work dimension on organizational citizenship behaviors.

According to the research findings, there is no significant relationship between organizational citizenship behavior and work-life balance in general. However, a low level relationship was found between some sub-dimensions of work life balance and organizational citizenship behavior and some sub-dimensions of work life balance predicted organizational citizenship behavior at various levels. Similarities can be seen between the findings of the research and the results of the other studies in the literature, and there are also studies that reach different results. Working with different occupational groups and sample sizes and lack of studies on teachers may cause this difference. Although the research conducted in public schools in a large-scale district

center and villages cannot be generalized, there is a relationship between the sub-dimensions of work-life balance and organizational citizenship behaviors.

Teachers can be productive without neglecting life, be directed to in-group work and awareness raising can be done through seminars. Pareto principles that emphasize conscious working principles and not hard work can be used in education (Brogan, 2010). Teachers can be informed about the need to spend quality time with their family outside the school in order to get rid of the stress of the workplace, not to deal with mobile phones and e-mail after a certain hour, and not to be deprived of sleep in order to protect their health. Seminars can be given to the spouses of female teachers who have intensive work tempo at school and at home, that life is common and that they should help female teachers in every subject. Encouraging teachers to do master's and doctoral degrees may have positive reflections on the increase in their professional satisfaction and thus on the balance of organization and work life. Increasing the economic level of teachers to the level of OECD countries so that teachers can produce new ideas and science can improve work life balances.

Individuals who see life as a job alone are in fact experiencing negative effects of emotional burnout, depersonalization and workaholic and deterioration in work-life balance. This situation indirectly has negative consequences on organizational citizenship behaviors. Teachers' work place is schools. Mutual negative effects between schools and social life can cause teachers to experience work-life imbalance. Harmonization of work and life will not only make the person happy but also increase the success of the workplace. This is an important issue for educational organizations. Because the success of the education system depends on the success of teachers.

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